

STAGES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SOCIAL PROTECTION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN, THE SOCIAL PROTECTION SYSTEM OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT:

This article reflects on the mistakes made in the field of social policy during the former Soviet regime and the reforms that have been implemented in the social field since the first years of our independence. Also, comments were given on the efforts being made to protect society members, ensure stability in the country, and glorify people. The article pays attention to the rational policy of the leader of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who strives for the priority of humanity, tolerance, and justice.

Keywords: poor family, social justice, social protection, social policy.

INTRODUCTION

Improving the mechanisms of inclusion of low-income and vulnerable sections of the population into the social assistance system and expanding their participation in the labor market is considered one of the urgent issues in our country. In this regard, the study of international experience, as well as the analysis of the social protection system of our country yesterday and today, and the mistakes and shortcomings made in the past in conclusion, issues of further development of the social protection system determine the relevance of today's topic.

Stage 1: Social protection system during the former union

It is known that during the former Union, social security was provided through centralized social security systems of the State. A comprehensive social assistance system had not yet been formed. During the Soviet era, our country became the main supplier of raw materials, and families became poorer year by year. The social policy of the ruling regime, its practice and shortcomings in solving the problems of improving people's well-being were especially manifested in the organization of social security of the population. In particular, the Soviet state excluded Uzbek farmers, who are the main part of the country's local population, from the scope of social security. Only urban residents, mostly workers (red fighters) and their families, were covered by the social security system, a policy that remained in place for decades to come. Villagers are not at all socially protected by the state. They ate their own sorrows. One of the main types of social security is a certain amount of allowance for the unemployed, which is not enough to meet the needs of these people. In addition, some sections of the society were deprived of the right to receive pensions and allowances. At the end of the 20s, in the context of economic recovery, positive changes in the field of public health protection were noticed. Several hospitals, dispensaries and first aid stations were operating. The increase of large enterprises, the involvement of women in production and public life required the establishment and increase of the network of maternity and child protection institutions. "From the middle of the 20s, mother and child homes, consultation

rooms for children were opened. In 1927, the scientific-research institute for motherhood and childhood protection was established.¹

The issue of women has always been a unique problem in human history. In the second half of the 20s, the Bolsheviks sharply resolved this socio-political issue, which involved the fate of millions of Turkestan women, based on their own standards.

We all know that the main goal of the Soviet authorities to "liberate" Uzbek women was to create a free labor force with new labor resources to solve the problems of the national economy by involving them in production. The fact that they are representatives of the fairer sex was not taken into account when recruiting them. These conditions seriously damaged their health.

One-fifth of the population of Uzbekistan lived in cities, uyezds, volosts, districts and districts, as well as working settlements. However, the social situation of all strata of the population is very difficult, even food and necessities there was no way to find the item. For example, textile fabrics, ordinary caliche and even matches were not available for sale. The famine of this period also brought heavy consequences to the population.² In the 1930s, all economic, political and spiritual activities in the Republic were carried out only with the permission of the Central Government. The republican government could not independently choose its own path in domestic and foreign policy and implement any measures without the permission of Moscow. He could not pursue an independent policy even in the payment of wages to workers, peasants and all sections of the population. As a result of very low wages, harsh working conditions, and lack of regulation of wages, workers would leave. As a result of falling production rates, increased absenteeism, and lack of staff, enterprises were experiencing economic stress. Factory workers performed very heavy manual labor, factory workshops were not equipped with labor protection equipment, the work of workers who worked outdoors in winter and summer was not particularly valued, and working in such conditions was very difficult. In some collective farms, labor was organized in a general way, i.e. as a whole team, and wages were distributed equally. Even the chairman of the collective farms did not know the work of each person in such collective farms and how to pay his wages. As a result of the equal distribution of wages to all, people lost the desire to work more. This method of socialist production would be an obstacle to the development of agriculture, not to the development of agriculture, as it is in industry. In the process of communalization, their lands and property were confiscated and generalized. Only one cow was left on each farm, and even the cow's calf was separated from its mother. Such a policy was not aimed at improving people's well-being, but at muting and grossly violating human rights. In Uzbekistan, the activity of the Shura government in the field of improving the material well-being of the people is one of the most important directions of social policy. was to do it. During this period, with the increase in the number of pensioners, the amount of allowances and payments paid from the state and local budgets in the republic increased. In addition to these payments, the state also covered the costs of homes for the disabled, employment of pensioners, labor training, treatment in sanatoriums and spas, prosthetics, etc. Coverage of these segments of the population with such payments was carried out mainly in large cities. In many cases, the rural population was not covered by social security. On August 28, 1932, the Council of

¹Kambarov. A "Social policy. Instructional instruction. FDU. 2012. B. 79.

²Koldosh Ergashev, Hojiakbar Hamidov. History of Uzbekistan. Publishing house named after Gafur Ghulam, Tashkent. 2015. Bet. 330.

Soviets made a decision "On providing for the families of soldiers conscripted into the Red Army"³ was of great importance, but there were many shortcomings in the work of this field. Although on paper, soldiers' families did not benefit from benefits. Because, due to the lack of specialist personnel, the decisions were not communicated to the people, or even when the decisions were received, they were not implemented in practice. Pensions were not delivered to their owners or funds were not used. In some places, the list of families called up for military service was not known. This situation in the republic was a sign of the coldness and lack of management of the city and district executive committees, and the employees of the social security agencies, as well as the complete disregard and lack of control over the work of this sector. On May 1935 "On the Work of Social Security Bodies" of the Council of the Soviets of the Uzbek SSR, on May 7, 1936 of the Central Committee of the Uzbek SSR "On the Reconstruction of Social Security Work in the Uzbek SSR "about"⁴ and a number of other documents have analyzed gross defects in the work of social welfare bodies in the republic together with achievements. During this period, funds were allocated for labor, war, old age and natural disabilities, national and local professional pensioners, academic pensioners, and there were certain benefits for them. They were often deprived of these benefits. Nevertheless, the introduction of such forms of benefit payments has gained a certain positive value for the well-being of the people. Employing the disabled in the republic, introducing labor education among them, that is, the practical work of directing them to the profession through production workshops (production artels) became noteworthy. But there were many problems in this field as well, which further complicated the situation and quickly crippled the industry. Soon, the All-Uzbek Disabled People's Cooperative Association, which leads production cooperatives of disabled people, will be dissolved. Mistakes and abuses committed in social policy during this period, gross violation of humanitarian laws, lack of development of rules for payment of wages suitable for work, issues of reckless attitude in social protection of the population and, first of all, its vulnerable groups, are today It is also more important from the point of view of being a historical lesson at a time when Uzbekistan wants to take steps to conduct an independent economic policy that responds to the interests of the people. The first experiments, the first measures are not always free from defects, but the abuses and injustices of social policy in the era of the "Red Empire" dominated by administrative courts should not be repeated.

II stage. Social protection system during the years of independence

After the independence of Uzbekistan, in the process of transition from the centralized planned economic system to the socially oriented market economy, ensuring the social protection of the population was considered as an important direction of the state policy. From the 90s of the 20th century, it began to acquire a new meaning in accordance with the changing reforms based on the transition to a market economy. Realization of identity, restoration of nationality brought innovation to the social protection system. As a result of the strong social policy of the state, the statistical indicator of unemployment in the country was 0.5-0.6%. Households, small and medium businesses were developed. As a result of the changes in the areas of service to the population, the rights of consumers have been ensured.

³Rahmonov. T. From the history of social policy in Uzbekistan. Scientific and educational association of intellectuals of Uzbekistan. Tashkent-1992. 17 – p.

⁴Rahmonov. T. From the history of social policy in Uzbekistan. Scientific and educational association of intellectuals of Uzbekistan. Tashkent-1992. 18 – p.

Maintaining the purchasing power of the soum, preventing inflation, establishing permanent state control over commerce, and establishing order in other areas developed social protection. In the early days of independence, it was known that social policy is the need of the times for our country. It would not be wrong to say that at the heart of all the reforms carried out in our country was paying attention to people, providing them with a comfortable life and creating decent living conditions. In the first economic crisis years of independence, the state used many methods to normalize the standard of living of people. In particular, salaries, stipends, pensions and allowances, and various other benefits, which are constantly increasing, have been introduced. In this process, issues of all-round support for the rights and interests of the underprivileged population, children and young people in the center of the reforms, such as their education, occupation, and access to qualified medical services, were considered as the main duty of the main state. During the years of independence, a system of social protection of the population was formed. The concept of social protection of the population and material support of low-income families has been implemented since the first years of independence. At this point, the first President said, "One of the most important rules that is the basis of Uzbekistan's path of renewal and development is to carry out a strong social policy in advance at all stages of the transition to a market economy. All other rules are subordinated to solving social tasks, creating a strict guarantee in the field of social protection of the population."⁵, the recollection of his thoughts shows how relevant the topic is.

Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev's reforms in the social protection system

We have gained a lot of experience in this field as a result of the strong social policy since independence. Even in today's reforming Uzbekistan, social protection is considered as the main link of reforms. "The main goal of our reforms in this direction is to turn the new Uzbekistan into a country of people who are satisfied with their lives and happy, and into a comprehensively developed social space"⁶the head of our state described the image of the new Uzbekistan.

At this point, we should also note that since the early days of independence, Uzbekistan has been gradually implementing socio-economic reforms. As a result of this, in 2011, the World Bank removed Uzbekistan from the list of low-income countries and included it in the lower level of the list of middle-income countries, as an example of reforms. Currently, about 16% of the population of Uzbekistan lives in poverty, 75% of them live in rural areas. One of the complex problems facing the country is the lack of employment opportunities, and the gap between rural and urban districts remains large. The high level of unemployment and low monthly salaries lead to mass labor migration of the population to Russia, Kazakhstan, Turkey and South Korea.⁷As a result of the drying up of the Aral Sea, environmental, socio-economic problems are increasing. Along with the negative impact on the lifestyle of the population, providing them with drinking water is gaining urgent importance. We have made significant progress in reducing poverty in recent years. According to statistics, the level of poverty in our country decreased from 28% in 2001 to 15% in 2016. This is definitely the result of

⁵Karimov, I.A. Uzbekistan towards a great future. T., Uzbekistan. 1998. Page 127

⁶Shavkat Mirziyoyev New Uzbekistan strategy. - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" publishing house, 2021. Page. 199.

⁷Study guide for studying and promoting the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 75th session of the United Nations General Assembly. Tashkent. "Spirituality". 2021. Page 231.

creating jobs in the villages and paying attention to the population in need of social protection. Today, great changes are being made aimed at social protection in order to ensure the social needs of every person. Currently, thanks to the wise policy of the head of our country, we have managed to reduce poverty by half in a very short period of time.

Today's humane policy of social support for low-income families is the essence of the welfare state. The fact that more than fifty percent of state funds are allocated to this sector is a sign of a welfare state. The social obligations of the state were further expanded in the newly adopted constitution. Including employment, unemployment protection, poverty reduction, etc. Also, the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy was approved by the Presidential Decree (PF-158, dated September 11, 2023) and the Presidential Decree on its timely and quality implementation in 2023 (PQ-300, dated September 11, 2023).) was accepted. According to the decree, the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy consists of the following 5 priority areas and 100 goals:

- create suitable conditions for every person to realize his potential;
- ensuring the well-being of the population through sustainable economic growth;
- conservation of water resources and environmental protection;
- ensuring the rule of law, organizing public administration at the service of the people;
- "consistent continuation of the policy based on the principle of "safe and peaceful state".

In the project of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, at least 50 percent of the houses being built under the "My First House" program should be allocated for low-income and young families, or the procedure for returning the value added tax calculated for the housing purchased by them makes every needy family happy. Also, connect to the information system "Unified Register of Social Protection" designed to keep records of social benefits for low-income families, start accepting applications for social benefits for low-income families in the district through the "Unified Register of Social Protection" eatorganizing the use of the information system "Unified Register of Social Protection" in the district, the low-income population "To organize the allocation of allowances through the information system of the Unified Register of Social Protection, provide legal services to itself in order to ensure continuous use of the system, to provide legal advice to small businesses and low-income residents, to introduce a new system of accepting their proposals and initiatives, to create the possibility of preparing legal documents without the participation of lawyers display The tasks of introducing the "Legal Tech" information system are defined.

In these areas, following the principle of social justice, supporting the needy sections of the population and reducing poverty has been raised to the level of state policy. To date, the number of people receiving social benefits has increased by almost 1.5 times. A lot of money is allocated from the state budget for social protection of this category and restoration of our economy. Recently, a practical, purposeful and effective system of social protection and identification of needy families has been established through the system of going from house to house. Also, financial support is provided to children of families who have lost their breadwinners and children with disabilities who are in need of financial assistance. In addition, as Uzbekistan declares itself a social state in the Constitution, the principle of humanitarianism becomes the main pillar of state policy. Reducing poverty in our country today

The principle of humanitarianism lies behind the work carried out in this regard, in particular, the support of the needy strata of the population through systems such as "Women's

Notebook" and "Iron Notebook". As a practical expression of the principle of humanitarianism, it is possible to cite social services and assistance that are identified and provided through the information system "Unified Register of Social Protection". For example, allowances for families with children under 18 years of age, allowances for child care until the age of 3, and monthly monetary compensation for financial assistance to low-income families are determined through this system. The state provides benefits and social guarantees to families with many children in accordance with the law. The Family and Women's Committee developed an electronic system for working with the "Women's Notebook". Through this system, the application of a woman in need of social protection to be included in the "Women's Register" is accepted and the results of the review of this application are given. Also, the introduction of the electronic system, such as the types of assistance provided to women included in the "Women's Register" and the registration of women receiving assistance through the "Women's Register", is giving the expected results.

In the 70th goal of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026, in the 71st goal of supporting young families, tasks such as ensuring the continuity of education in the family, educational institutions and the neighborhood are set. Many laws and regulations in order to strengthen state support for legal, social, economic, spiritual and moral interests and welfare documents are being accepted. For example, in the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 7, 2022, protection of the rights and legal interests of women in the country, increase of economic, social and political activity of women, protection of women's health, training of women in the profession such as providing training and employment, wide involvement of women in entrepreneurship, social support for women in need, ensuring gender equality measures for the implementation of the issues were determined.

CONCLUSION:

A strong social policy is implemented in the republic is one of the most important principles of democratic reform. Social policy is an important component of state policy and regulates all processes in the social sphere. At the same time, it is a process that helps to make the human factor as invisible as possible. The priority goal of our state's policy today is to create a peaceful, comfortable and prosperous life for everyone living in our country. One of the important areas of social policy is social protection issues. Social protection, first of all, refers to the work of improving the life of the poor strata of the population. It is only through social policy that it is possible to carry out activities related to the full realization of the socio-economic and legal interests of the individual, and to increase the well-being of families and every person.

Of course, the living conditions of each member of the population and society to increase, expand opportunities for education, health strengthening, participation in socially useful work as a workforce raising the capacity to achieve is a priority of the social policy of our country is one of the directions. In this sense, population protection the first and main task in providing is to improve a person, it is related to increasing its position and prestige in the family and society.

Therefore, the humanitarianism of the society is the economic of the country not by how high the potential is, but by this potential for the well-being and comprehensive development of a person is evaluated by orientation. Nowadays, improvement of the social security system is one of the most pressing issues in market relations. Because of all the economic reforms and measures being carried out in the country everything is for man. Therefore, the poor of the

population, a stratum that cannot compete in the labor market: the poor families, unemployed, disabled, children, students, elderly, disabled, social protection of the bereaved, creating more opportunities for them is considered as the main goal.

Addressed social protection has been widely introduced in the country to those who clearly and truly need it, families delivery is ensured. Because the first market economy the requirement is accuracy and ability to allocate funds correctly. According to the experience of countries that have reformed the social protection system, the implementation of targeted social protection makes it possible to save a large amount of money at the expense of the state. This means that the government's necessary funding for social protection is at a moderate level taking necessary measures to ensure separation indicates.

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